

Nickel(II) and Copper(II) Complexes of 5-Aryl-1-phenylpent-1-yn-3,5-diones

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Although a large number of β -diketones and their related compounds are known to form complexes with several metals¹, comparatively less work has been done on the transition metal complexes of acetylenic β -diketones probably due to the difficulties encountered in their synthesis. Hence, we report here the synthesis and characterisation of nickel(II) and copper(II) complexes of 5-aryl-1-phenylpent-1-yn-3,5-diones.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data for the prepared metal complexes (Table 1) suggest a 1 : 2 stoichiometry of the general formula $M L_2 \cdot 2H_2O$, where $L = 5$ -aryl-1-phenylpent-1-yn-3,5-diones ($ph-C \equiv CO=CH_2-CO-R$); $M = Ni^{II}$ and Cu^{II} ; $R = C_6H_5$, $p-CH_3OC_6H_4$, $p-CH_3C_6H_4$, $p-BrC_6H_4$, $p-ClC_6H_4$. All the complexes are found to be non-electrolytes in N,N -dimethylformamide medium as indicated by their low values of molar conductivity at 25° (Table 1).

The main IR bands of the complexes are given in Table 1. One of the two carbonyl oxygen atoms of the ligand molecules tends to be in the enol form. The carbonyl oxygen atom adjacent to acetylenic ($C \equiv C$) group may be the more stable one. The

enolised hydrogen was suggested to be in an intramolecular hydrogen bonding² with $C=O$ group of carbon-3. The disappearance of a band in the range 3000–3250 cm^{-1} , for the free ligands, attributed to ν_{OH} involving in intramolecular hydrogen bonding, indicates that the enolisation of $C=O$ of carbon-5 may occur only in solution. The spectra of all the complexes exhibit a broad band at 3220–3250 cm^{-1} attributed to hydrogen-bonded coordinated water³. This is in harmony with the results of the elemental analyses (Table 1) which suggest the presence of water molecules in the complexes. The spectra of the free ligands show a broad band at 1600–1625 cm^{-1} characteristic of β -diketones, besides the acetylenic stretching band at 2220–2258 cm^{-1} . The former band shows a shift towards lower values (1600–1570 cm^{-1}) suggesting the coordination of carbonyl oxygen atom. Careful examination of the spectra of the complexes indicates the enolisation and deprotonation of $C=O$ of carbon-5 and, therefore, the ligands may interact with the central metal ions (Ni^{II} , Cu^{II}) in the enol form as substantiated by appearance of ν_{C-O} band at 1270–1285 cm^{-1} in spectra of all the complexes. Furthermore, the presence of $M-O$ vibration is verified by the appearance of new bands in the frequency range⁴ 470–

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL, PHYSICAL AND IR SPECTRAL (cm^{-1}) DATA OF $M(ph-C \equiv C-\overset{O}{\parallel}C-CH=\overset{O}{\parallel}C-R)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$

M	R	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			Λ $\Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$	$\nu_{C \equiv O}$	ν_{OH}	ν_{C-O}	ν_{M-O}
		C	H	M					
Ni	$p-CH_3C_6H_4$	70.4 (70.0)	5.0 (4.8)	9.8 (9.5)	7.3	1580	3230	1280	450
Ni	$p-CH_3OC_6H_4$	68.2 (68.5)	4.9 (4.6)	9.4 (9.0)	5.8	1590	3220	1278	445
Ni	C_6H_5	73.0 (73.3)	5.3 (5.0)	10.1 (9.9)	9.6	1575	3246	1270	440
Ni	$p-ClC_6H_4$	65.4 (65.6)	4.8 (4.5)	9.2 (8.9)	10.8	1595	3250	1275	448
Ni	$p-BrC_6H_4$	57.9 (57.8)	4.5 (4.0)	8.1 (7.8)	12.3	1600	3225	1280	455
Cu	$p-CH_3C_6H_4$	69.7 (69.5)	4.9 (4.8)	10.5 (10.2)	7.9	1585	3235	1285	460
Cu	$p-CH_3OC_6H_4$	66.5 (66.1)	4.7 (4.5)	9.6 (9.7)	14.5	1590	3228	1280	470
Cu	C_6H_5	73.1 (72.7)	5.3 (5.0)	10.5 (10.6)	6.8	1600	3238	1270	465
Cu	$p-ClC_6H_4$	65.6 (65.2)	4.8 (4.5)	9.9 (9.5)	10.0	1595	3240	1275	445
Cu	$p-BrC_6H_4$	57.7 (57.4)	4.2 (3.9)	8.8 (8.4)	9.8	1588	3250	1283	450

440 cm^{-1} . From the foregoing discussion, it can be deduced that 5-aryl-1-phenylpent-1-yn-3,5-diones has coordinated to the metal ion as monobasic O–O donor bidentate ligands through their carbonyl oxygen of C-3 and enolised negatively charged oxygen of C-5 (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1

The magnetic moment values for the nickel(II) complexes (2.98–3.20 B.M.) are in favour of octahedral geometry around the central metal ion. This geometry is further supported by the electronic spectral data which include two bands at 500–550 and 420–450 nm related to the transitions ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$, respectively. The band at 260–300 nm may be ascribed to charge transfer transition. The μ_{eff} values for the copper(II) complexes lie in the range 1.78–1.84 B.M. The electronic spectra of the copper(II) complexes exhibit a band at 330–360 nm which may be attributed to intramolecular charge transfer. The bands due to $d-d$ transitions do not appear in their normal of wavelength at longer values. The observations suggest a distorted octahedral geometry for the copper(II) complexes.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of reagent grade (B.D.H. or Merck). 5-Aryl-1-phenylpent-1-yn-3,5-diones were prepared according to the reported procedure⁵.

The metal complexes were prepared by stirring ethanolic solutions of $\text{Ni}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ or $\text{Cu}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.1 mol) and 5-aryl-1-phenylpent-1-yn-3,5-diones (0.2 mol) for 2 h, and the resulting solids were washed with ethanol and dried.

Infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Beckman IR 20 spectrophotometer and electronic spectra (DMF) on a Spectronic 200 spectrophotometer. Conductance was measured at 25° in DMF using a YSI 31 conductivity bridge. The magnetic measurement was carried out by the Gouy method at room temperature, the apparatus being calibrated with mercury tetrathiocyanatocobaltate(II). Diamagnetic corrections were made by using Pascal's constants. Elemental analyses were carried out in the Microanalytical Laboratory, Faculty of Science, Cairo University.

References

1. M. K. MISRA and D. V. RAMANARAGO, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1970, **8**, 86; N. N. GHOSH and S MAULIK, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **46**, 675; A. M. EL-ATRASH, F. M. EIZAWAWI and R. H. RAMADAN, *Egypt. J. Chem.*, 1980, **23**, 113; A. M. A. HASSAAN, E. M. SOLIMAN and A. M. EL-ROUDI, *Polyhedron*, 1989, **8**, 925; M. F. ISKANDER, L. EL-SAYED, A. F. M. HEVNY and S. E. ZAYAN, *J. Inorg Nucl. Chem.*, 1976, **38**, 2209; A. EL-TOUKY, A. F. M. HEVNY, L. EL-SAYED and M. F. ISKANDER, *Mh. Chem.*, 1982, **113**, 171; Y. NKAMESWARARAO and PRABHAKARARAO, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1988, **27**, 555; A. A. M. ALY, M. S. EL-MELIGY and A. S. A. ZIDAN, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1989, **14**, 366; G. A. M. HUSSEIN, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1991, **186**, 187.
2. I. E. EL-KHOLY, M. M. MISHRIKEY and M. G. MAREI, *J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1982, **19**, 1421.
3. L. G. THIÉRIOT, G. O. CARLISLE and H. J. HU, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1969, **31**, 3303.
4. J. A. FANIRAN, K. S. PATEL and L. O. NELSON, *J. Inorg Nucl. Chem.*, 1976, **38**, 77.
5. I. E. EL-KHOLY, M. G. MAREI and M. M. MISHRIKEY, *J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1979, **16**, 737.

Synthesis and Study of Mixed-ligand Complexes of Benzoylacetone with some Schiff Bases

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Several workers¹ reported mixed ligand complexes of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} with Schiff bases as bidentate ligands, and several reviews have appeared on metal β -diketone complexes². Hence, the above complexes from 2-hydroxy-5-carboxyacetophenone Schiff bases and benzoylacetone, have been studied.

Results and Discussion

The Ni^{II} complexes were found to be diamagnetic (Table 1). The conductivity measurements of the complexes revealed their non-electrolytic nature, giving low molar conductivity values.

TABLE I—DETAILS OF SCHIFF BASES AND COMPLEXES

Sl. no.	R ₁	R ₂	Cu ^{II} complex		μ _{eff} B.M.	Ni ^{II} complex	
			Analysis % :			Analysis % :	
			Found/(Calcd.)	Found/(Calcd.)		N	Ni
1.	H	H ₁	2.81 (2.92)	12.89 (13.27)	2.12	2.89 (2.97)	12.18 (12.39)
2.	H	Cl	2.65 (2.72)	12.17 (12.38)	2.05	2.61 (2.75)	11.02 (11.55)
3.	Cl	H	2.65 (2.72)	12.17 (12.28)	2.10	2.65 (2.75)	11.15 (11.55)
4.	NO ₂	Cl	4.95 (5.01)	11.17 (11.38)	2.11	5.0 (5.06)	10.28 (10.61)
5.	H	NO ₂	5.28 (5.34)	11.96 (12.13)	1.99	5.25 (5.39)	10.91 (11.31)
6.	NO ₂	H	5.29 (5.34)	11.94 (12.13)	1.97	5.25 (5.39)	11.17 (11.31)
7.	CH ₃	H	2.79 (2.84)	12.51 (12.90)	2.15	2.81 (2.87)	11.82 (12.03)
8.	Br	H	2.43 (2.51)	11.09 (11.40)	2.12	2.40 (2.53)	10.28 (10.62)
9.	MeO	H	2.33 (2.75)	12.20 (12.40)	2.02	2.65 (2.78)	11.18 (11.65)
10.	EtO	H	2.58 (2.68)	12.05 (12.16)	2.13	2.58 (2.70)	10.94 (11.34)
11.	NO ₂	MeO	4.98 (5.05)	11.20 (11.48)	2.12	5.02 (5.10)	10.71 (10.70)

The ligand ir band due to C=N (1 650 cm⁻¹) shifted to the lower side (1 600 cm⁻¹) on the complex formation. The ligand bands due to phenolic OH (1 200 cm⁻¹) disappeared in the complexes. These indicate coordination through azomethine nitrogen and phenolic oxygen atom³. The bands due to enolic C=O in benzoylacetone (1 640 cm⁻¹) shifted to lower side (1 560 cm⁻¹) in the complexes, indicating coordination through C=O and involvement of enolic OH in the complex formation⁴.

On the basis of the above results, the complexes were assigned the following structure.

Experimental

A mixture of dry 4-hydroxybenzoic acid (13.8 g, 0.1 mol) and acetic anhydride (12.0 ml, 0.1 mol) containing a few drops of concentrated H₂SO₄, was heated in a water-bath for 1 h, then cooled and

treated with ice-cold water. The product 4-acetoxybenzoic acid (m.p. 189°) was converted into the corresponding hydroxyketone, HCAP (m.p. 240°) by Fries migration.

The Schiff bases were prepared by condensing HCAP with various arylamines according to the standard method⁵. HCAP (1.8 g, 0.01 mol) dissolved in ethanol was mixed with the solution of amines (0.01 mol) in ethanol. The mixture was refluxed for 3 h, then cooled and treated with cold water to yield the product.

Mixed ligand complexes: The Schiff base in ethanol (50 ml, 0.01 mol) was mixed with benzoylacetone in ethanol (25 ml, 0.02 mol) and metal solution (10 ml, 0.05 mol) was then added dropwise with constant stirring. The mixture having a 1 : 1 : 1 molar ratio, was vigorously stirred for 0.5 h at 50° and then refluxed for 1.5 h. The coloured complexes, separated on cooling, were filtered and washed with ethanol and hot water. The complexes formed in the pH range 6.5–7.5 for Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} were found to be insoluble in common organic solvents but soluble in glacial acetic acid. The complexes were also found to be stable for weeks without any change.

The gravimetric determinations along with the metal content was determined by first decomposing the complex with HClO₄ and then titrating the solution with standard EDTA solution. Molecular weight was determined by Rast's method. The complexes were quantitatively analysed for their nitrogen content. Magnetic susceptibility was measured by Gouy method at 28°. Conductance of the complexes in glacial acetic acid was measured on a Toshniwal conductivity bridge.

References

1. B. T. THAKER and P. K. BHATTACHARYA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1979, **18**, 371; C. NATRAJAN, R. FRANCIS, ASHOK and M. PALANIANDAVAR, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1979, **18**, 364; A. DAS, A. BAGCHI and S. R. SAHA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1990, **29**, 361; V. K. PATEL, A. M. VASANWALA and C. R. JEJURKAR, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1989, **28**, 719.
2. D. P. GRADDON, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1969, **4**, 1; O. GIBSON, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1969, **4**, 225; J. J. FORTMAN and R. E. SIVERS, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1971, **6**, 331; R. C. MEHROTRA, R. BOHRA and D. P. GAUR, "Metal β-diketonates and Allied Derivatives", Academic, New York, 1978.
3. M. A. ALI and R. Bose, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1977, **39**, 265; J. E. CAVACIS, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part A*, 1967, **23**, 183.
4. J. R. DYER, "Application of Absorption Spectroscopy of Organic Compounds", Prentice-Hall of India, New Delhi, 1978, p. 34.
5. A. I. VOGL, "A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", 3rd. ed., ELBS, London, p. 653.